

STUDIES ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL ACTIVITY OF MIXTURES OF VANADIC
ACID AND TARTARIC ACID. PART IV. PHOTOREDUCTION OF
VANADIC ACID IN CIRCULARLY POLARISED LIGHT.
INDUCED CIRCULAR DICHROISM

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The influence of *d*- and *l*- circularly polarised light on the photoreduction of vanadic acid sol by tartaric acid and of mixtures of sodium meta-vanadate and tartaric acid, has been studied. Differences in the velocity of the reaction and circular dichroism in the reaction product are observed. It has also been found that reduced vanadic acid sol exhibits circular dichroism in the visible region on exposure to circularly polarised light.

The photoreduction of (a) vanadic acid (as meta-vanadate) by tartaric acid in ordinary light, and (b) circularly dichroic vanadic acid sol in circularly polarised light, has been described in the previous papers of this series (Rama Char, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 507, 605). In the present investigation, the influence of circularly polarised light on (i) reaction (a), (ii) photochemically active systems containing undichroic vanadic acid sol, and (iii) reduced vanadic acid sol, has been studied.

A. Photoreduction of Vanadic Acid Sol: Induced Dichroism

The experimental arrangement, the method of preparation of the sol, etc., are the same as those described before (Rama Char, *loc. cit.*). The photoreduction was studied with freshly prepared sol as well as sol pre-excited in unpolarised light. Measurements of ellipticity (Rama Char, *ibid.*, 1941, 18, 563) showed that the sol did not develop any dichroism on excitation in unpolarised light for 5 hours. The sol at p_H 5.3 was mixed with the reductant; after exposure to *d*- and *l*- circularly polarised light, the solutions were estimated for vanadium (V^5) and the dichroism (as ellipticity) measured. The reductants were recrystallised before use.

There is no dark reaction with mixtures of sol and tartaric acid. The results obtained for the velocity of the reaction in *d*- and *l*-lights are given below. dx/dt refers throughout to the number of g. mols transformed per minute.

Conc. of potassium tartrate = 0.10 *M*. Radiation = whole visible. $p_H = 5.5$. Temp. = 25°. Conc. vanadic acid sol = 0.05 *M*. Period of excitation of sol = 5 hours. $I_{abs.} = 1384$ ergs (in all cases). Period of exposure of reaction mixture = 4½ hours. Intensity of exciting radiation for sol = 7784 ergs (Tables I and II)

TABLE I

Reaction mixture exposed to	Unexcited sol. $dx/dt \times 10^5$.		Sol excited in unpolarised light. $dx/dt \times 10^5$.	
	<i>d</i> -light.	<i>l</i> -light.	<i>d</i> -light.	<i>l</i> -light.
Reductant <i>d</i> -tartrate	1.94	1.39	2.08	1.53
<i>l</i> - " "	1.94	1.34	2.13	1.57
<i>dl</i> - " "	1.94	1.34	2.08	1.53
Racemic* tartrate	1.94	1.39	2.04	1.53

TABLE II

Wave-length.	Length of solution.	Ellipticity developed on exposure to	
		<i>d</i> -light.	<i>l</i> -light.
5780 Å	4 cm.	-0.30°	—
5460	3	-0.80	-0.30°
5200	1	-0.50	-0.40
4916	0.2	-0.15	-0.10

The results show that, irrespective of the reductant used, the velocity of the reaction is greater in *d*-light than in *l*-light, whether the sol is unexcited or pre-excited in unpolarised light. The quantum efficiency γ of the photo-process is of the order of 0.4 (mean value). The corresponding values for the circular dichroism developed in these mixtures after exposure to *d*- and *l*-light are given above. The mixtures are not initially (*i.e.*, before reaction) dichroic, nor do they develop dichroism on keeping in the dark for 6 hours. Systematic measurements showed that, like the velocity of the reaction, the ellipticity developed in the reaction mixture is independent of (i) the nature of the reductant used, *d*-, *l*-, or racemic-tartrate, and (ii) whether the sol is unexcited or pre-excited in unpolarised light. As such the ellipticity values for a typical set of mixtures of sol and reductant are given throughout.

The ellipticity (Table II) has a negative sign, *i.e.*, the anisotropy factor is negative (Rama Char, *loc. cit.*), whether the mixture is exposed to *d*- or *l*-light; the magnitude is always greater for exposures to *d*-light, which gives the greater value for the reaction velocity, than to *l*-light. The observed dichroism lies in the yellow, green and blue regions which are effective for the photoreduction.

B. Photoreduction of Mixtures of Sodium meta-vanadate and Tartaric Acid:
Induced Dichroism

For the reaction in the ultraviolet, circularly polarised light was obtained by the combination of a Glans polarising prism and a Carl-Zeiss quarter-wave plate. The velocity of the reaction in *d*- and *l*-light (visible and ultraviolet) is given below. T refers to the tartrate ion. There is no dark reaction.

TABLE III

Conc. of $H_2T = 0.05 M$. Radiation = whole visible. Conc. $NaVO_3 = 0.1 M$. Period of exposure = 6 hours. $\phi_n = 5.4$. Temp. = 25° .
 $I_{obs.} = 4583$ ergs. (in all cases).
 $dx/dt \times 10^5$

Polarised light	<i>d</i> - H_2T	<i>l</i> - H_2T	Racemic- H_2T	γ (mean value).
<i>d</i> -circular	2.91	2.91	2.91	0.35
<i>l</i> - "	2.22	2.22	2.22	

TABLE IV

$\lambda = 3660 \text{ \AA}$ (Schott and Gen ultraviolet filter). $I_{obs.} = 4065$ ergs (in all cases).
Other conditions same as in Table III.
 $dx/dt \times 10^5$

Polarised light	<i>d</i> - H_2T	<i>l</i> - H_2T	Racemic- H_2T	γ (mean value)
<i>l</i> -circular	5.31	5.31	5.31	0.35
<i>d</i> - "	4.26	4.26	4.26	

For visible light, the velocity of the photoreduction is greater in *d*-light than in *l*-light, the reverse being the case in the ultraviolet, and in both cases it is independent of the reductant. Ghosh *et al* (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 495, 617) have found that in ultraviolet light, photochemical reactions using vanadic acid sol either as a photo-oxidant or as a sensitiser give a greater value for the velocity in *l*-light. The circular dichroism developed in the reaction mixture on exposure to visible light is independent of the reductant, *d*-, *l*- or racemic tartaric acid; the values for a typical set of mixtures are given below.

TABLE V

Conditions same as in Table III.

Wave-length.	Length of sol.	Ellipticity developed on exposure to <i>d</i> -light.	<i>l</i> -light.
5780 $\text{\AA}$	3 cm.	-0.35°	—
5460	2	-0.63	-0.35°
5200	0.5	-0.84	-0.36
4916	0.1	-0.56	-0.35

The results are of the same type as those obtained in the photoreduction of vanadic acid sol. The wave-lengths in which dichroism is observed are effective for the photoreduction.

The influence of *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised visible light on the photoreduction at μ 5.0 to 5.5 of undichroic vanadic acid sol as well as of vanadate-tartaric acid mixtures leads to some significant results. The velocity of the reaction and the circular dichroism (which is always negative) developed is (i) independent of the reductant, and (ii) greater for exposures to *d*-light than to *l*-light. These observations suggest the possibility that the dichroism developed in all the above cases is due to the action of *d*- and *l*-light on the reduced vanadic acid sol (or reduced vanadate-tartaric acid mixture) which is produced as a result of photoreduction: $V^5 \rightarrow V^4$. The experiments that were carried out to test this hypothesis are described below.

C. Induced Dichroism in Reduced Vanadic Acid Sol

The complete reduction of 0.1M vanadic acid sol at μ 5.3 was effected by exposing mixtures of sol and an excess of potassium racemic-tartrate (0.16M) or racemic-mandelate (0.16M) to light for 8 hours. The reduction of the sol by hydrazine hydrate was carried out in the dark. The reduced solutions were estimated to ensure complete reduction. These solutions have no dichroism in visible light, nor do they develop any on keeping in the dark for 5 hours. But dichroism is induced in them on exposure to *d*- and *l*-light; the results are given below; titrations performed after exposure showed that there was no change in the concentration of the sol.

TABLE VI

Conc. of reduced vanadic acid sol = 0.05 M. Radiation = whole visible. Period of exposure of sol = 5 hours. Intensity of exciting radiation = 7784 ergs (in all cases).
 (a) Sol reduced by racemic tartrate; (b) sol reduced by racemic mandelate; (c) sol reduced by hydrazine hydrate.

Wave-length.	Length of solution.	Ellipticity developed on exposure to		Length of solution.	Ellipticity developed on exposure to		Length of solution.	Ellipticity developed on exposure to	
		<i>d</i> -light.	<i>l</i> -light.		<i>d</i> -light.	<i>l</i> -light.		<i>d</i> -light.	<i>l</i> -light.
(a) 5780 Å	4 cm.	-0.12°	+0.09°	(b) 3 cm.	-0.48°	-0.32°	(c) 3 cm.	-0.90°	-0.60°
5460	4	-0.15	-0.09	2	-0.48	-0.32	2	-0.90	-0.60
5200	3	-0.18	-0.12	2	-0.80	-0.56	1	-0.75	-0.50
4916	2	-0.09	-0.06	1	-0.24	-0.16	1	-0.45	-0.30

Dichroism is developed irrespective of the reductant used for reducing the sol. The ellipticity (just as in sections A and B) is always negative and is greater for exposures to *d*-light. The wave-length region in which dichroism is observed is the same as in sections A and B.

The observations made in sections A, B and C indicate that the induced dichroism that is observed in sections A and B is due to the action of *d*- and *l*-light on the reduced sol that is produced as a result of photoreduction. The induced dichroism leads to differences in light absorption and therefore to differences in reaction velocity in *d*- and *l*-light.

The author wishes to express his thanks to Sir J. C. Ghosh, Kt., D.Sc., F.N.I., for his kind interest and valuable suggestions during the investigation.

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Received November 12, 1943.